

ENTRUST

Project Title	ENsuring Secure and Safe CMD Design with Zero TRUST Principles		
Project Acronym	ENTRUST		
Grant Agreement No	101095634	Type of Action	Research and Innovation Action
Call / Topic	HORIZON-HLTH-2022-IND-13-01		

D1.1 Project Handbook

Work Package	WP1 – Project Management		
Lead Beneficiary	UNIS		
Contributing Beneficiaries	UBITECH		
Due Date	31.03.2023	Actual Date of Submission	30.03.2023
Version	1.0		
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Abstract	This report provides the definition of the processes and mechanisms to be utilized and followed during the lifecycle of ENTRUST project towards the successful execution of its tasks and achievement of its objectives.		
Keywords	Reporting procedure, Deliverables submission, Quality Management, Risk management		

Versioning and contribution history

Version	Date	Author	Notes
0.1	16.01.2023	Dr. Stavroula-Isidora Giannakandropoulou (UNIS)	Table of Contents
0.2	24.01.2023	Dr. Stavroula-Isidora Giannakandropoulou (UNIS)	Table of Contents, Introduction
0.3	07.02.2023	Dr. Stavroula-Isidora Giannakandropoulou (UNIS)	Implementation Aspects
0.4	09.02.2023	Dr. Stavroula-Isidora Giannakandropoulou (UNIS), Eleni-Nora Papatsoutsou (UBITECH)	Consortium Composition, Contacts and Management Structure, Reporting Procedure and Payment Arrangements
0.5	16.02.2023	Dr. Stavroula-Isidora Giannakandropoulou (UNIS)	Payment Schedule, Deliverable's submission
0.6	21.02.2023	Dr. Stavroula-Isidora Giannakandropoulou (UNIS), Thomas Krousarlis (UBITECH)	Introduction, Deliverables and Quality Management
0.7	01.03.2023	Dr. Stavroula-Isidora Giannakandropoulou (UNIS), Thomas Krousarlis (UBITECH)	Communication amongst Consortium partners, Risk management plan overview
0.8	08.03.2023	Dr. Stavroula-Isidora Giannakandropoulou (UNIS), Thomas Krousarlis (UBITECH)	Risk management plan
0.9	10.03.2023	Dr. Stavroula-Isidora Giannakandropoulou (UNIS), Thomas Krousarlis (UBITECH)	General overview, List of tables, List of figures
0.95	27.03.2023	Bárbara Guerra, Marco Manso (PARTICLE), Elsa Katsorida (SENTIO)	Internal Review
1.0	30.03.2023	Dr. Stavroula-Isidora Giannakandropoulou (UNIS)	QA review and submission

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Project co-funded by the European Commission in the Horizon Programme		
Nature of the deliverable:	R	
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open	X
SEN	Sensitive, confidential to ENTRUST project and Commission Services	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

DMP: Data Management Plan

Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Term	Description
CA	Consortium Agreement
CEB	Common Exploitation Booster
CRM	Continuous Risk Management
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
EEAB	External Experts Advisory Board
EU	European Union
FRAND	Fair, Reasonable, and Non-Discriminatory
FS	Financial Statements
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HEU	Horizon Europe
IEC	Independent Ethics Committee
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ITC	International Trade Centre
NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement
PM	Person Month
PMI	Project Management Institute
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
ROL	Results Ownership List
RTD	Research and Technical Development
SEI	Software Engineering Institute
WIPO	World Intellectual Property Organisation
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

The specific deliverable entitled “Project Handbook” provides the definition of the processes and mechanisms to be utilised and followed during the lifecycle of ENTRUST project towards the successful execution of its tasks and achievement of its objectives. Its purpose is to identify the processes, the metrics and the supportive documentation that is required and needs to be defined and deployed to ensure the high-quality of ENTRUST deliverables and project management activities.

In the ENTRUST project, complying with the project management procedures falls under the responsibility of the Project Coordinator, as well as the Work Packages (WPs) leaders and Tasks leaders. Effective channels of internal communication have been established from M1 to exchange all the necessary information for the project implementation among the participants. The means for remotely conveying information for the ENTRUST purposes range from e-mail communication through dedicated mailing lists and teleconferencing facilities to an internal collaboration space for document management and task management activities. Regarding the project meetings, an analysis of expectations and responsibilities has been performed while a tentative schedule of project meetings for the whole implementation of the ENTRUST project has been prepared.

The implementation aspects regarding co-creation and consultation mechanisms, official and internal reporting procedures, decision-making and conflict resolution processes to be applied during the ENTRUST implementation have been defined in detail. Document control aspects regarding the documentation requirements, templates and naming conventions and versioning have been also specified and agreed.

Quality assurance of ENTRUST results is of high importance to the partnership. Hence, internal audit control mechanisms are utilized to support the submission of excellent results, applying appropriate corrective actions if deemed necessary. Specific quality procedure is to be followed within the consortium for the preparation of all project related deliverables.

In order to facilitate the internal review process, reviewers (apart from the Project Coordinator and the deliverable responsible partners) have been already assigned for each deliverable for timely planning of the anticipated effort.

Finally, the current deliverable provides the definition of a risk management plan by defining a continuous risk assessment and mitigation approach, as well as identifying an initial set of risks that will be monitored and further populated during the project execution.

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope and Purpose

The purpose of the present deliverable entitled “Project Handbook”, provides a quick overview of the project management structure and the most relevant managerial aspects to be followed, based on a proper implementation of the general mechanisms of work and setting the rules and responsibilities of the ENTRUST consortium. The objective is to ensure a high-quality progress of the work during the project’s lifetime. This includes the production of the deliverables and other project outcomes of high quality, the mechanisms for their submission and the internal review process, and which are the communication means among partners (i.e., meetings, mailing lists, project collaborative space).

In this context, the present deliverable aims to fulfil the following main objectives:

- Establish a quality management system in accordance with the ISO 9001 (Quality Management Systems - Requirements) standard [1];
- Assure the quality of the project deliverables and project management activities;
- Identify the quality responsibilities of all partners within the consortium;
- Ensure proper co-ordination and communication channels among partners during the project lifetime;
- Identify the potential risks of the project and evaluate their impact and exposure; while proactively designing risk elimination methods to guarantee the seamless and proper execution of the project’s tasks.

2 Consortium Composition, Contacts and Management Structure

2.1 Consortium and Participants Contacts

Official contact information of each of the Project Participants is included in the ENTRUST Grant Agreement (GA). The full list of project participants, along with subscription to mailing lists is maintained as a living document in the ENTRUST Project Repository as a document restricted to the consortium. Partners are responsible to inform about any modification of their representatives both the Project Coordinator and the Project Management **Steering Committee** or the respective WP leader, who will be responsible for informing the rest of members (if necessary).

2.2 Management Structure

The project management in ENTRUST will guarantee transparency and commitment to all engaged partners and thus, facilitate an unobstructed and successful project evolution. The overall project management of ENTRUST will comply with the following two major principles, namely the: (1) **Principle of creating an integrated project structure incorporating technical, scientific and partner coordination as well as issues of commonplace business operation**, based on the methodology of the Project Management Institute (PMI) and supported with state of-the-art management instruments; and (2) **Principle of achieving agreement upon all partners and guaranteeing the arrangement of spot of decision making** close to the responsible levels of execution as well as elevate them if necessary, concealing the reliable and trusted agreements in order to protect intellectual properties of all partners.

The project structure is designed to handle the most important aspects of management, namely decision-making, Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) policy, technical and administrative management, advisory functions and assessment. The overall management of the project is being facilitated by a consistent and formal approach. In any event, a detailed internal Project Plan is being defined in the preliminary stage of the project, to support the contractual Work Plan and to form the basis of the administrative structures and procedures to be used. The reporting lines and decision-making procedures are described in detail in the following sections.

The primary aim of this management structure is to be capable of responding to the needs of a Research and Innovation Action (RIA) without being intrusive or costly. The building-in of flexibility was one essential aspect while defining this structure. The management structure is shown in detail in the following figure (Figure 1).

Figure 1 – ENTRUST Management Structure

2.3 Project Bodies and Main Responsibilities

Description and duties of these entities (Figure 1) are fully described in the GA and are thus only briefly reported below (subsection 2.3.1).

2.3.1 General Assembly (GA)

GA will consist of representatives of each partner organisation. It constitutes the highest decision board and its main task is project governance. It has the overall responsibility of all technical, financial, legal, administrative, ethical and impact issues of the project. It monitors and assesses the project’s progress and makes amendments, where necessary. It is composed of the following interconnected working groups with distinct responsibilities:

Project Coordination & Management Team: UNIS is responsible for overseeing the entire project, including its administrative, technical, and scientific coordination. It : (i) monitors the planning and progress the project with respect to the objectives and targets; (ii) ensures that all deliverables will be available on time to the Commission and/or project partners; (iii) manages all the communications to/from the EU Commission, the periodic reporting and will organize the review meetings with the Project Officer (PO); (iv) ensures that the Consortium fulfils the recommendations received from the European Commission and the Experts evaluators; (v) maintains the Consortium Agreement (CA) and manages the IPRs (vi) collects financial statements and audit certificates, as required by the contract and for reporting the periodic financial summaries and resource efforts spent by each partner and (vii) manages the granted

EU contribution and the distribution of the funds to each partner according with the actual allocated efforts. Also, UNIS is responsible for the implementation of quality procedures and the quality assurance of deliverables. Additionally, UNIS will monitor, assess and evaluate the critical risks of the ENTRUST project.

Scientific & Technical Coordination Team: UBITECH has undertaken the technical coordination of the project, as to ensure a strong consistency between the scientific and technical WPs. It cooperates closely with the project's technical providers and WP Leaders to ensure that the scientific and technological objectives of the project are met with quality and in time. Also, UBITECH leads the scientific activities performed within the project and is responsible for resolving any issues of scientific and technical nature that might occur.

Legal & Ethics Monitoring Team: FN, along with UNIS, UBI, RA, and MI, are working towards defining how research will be executed ensuring the ethical & legal compliance of the ENTRUST framework, demonstrators and data to the EU and national legislation (including GDPR), analysing the ethical compliance of project's outcomes against applicable laws and regulations, providing suitable guidelines and recommendations.

Work Package Leaders Team: Composed of ENTRUST's WP and Task leaders, this team is responsible for managing the corresponding work packages as self-contained entities. The responsibilities of each member of the team include coordinating, monitoring, and assessing the progress of the assigned work package, based on the reports of the task leaders, to ensure that output performance, budget, and timelines are met. In cooperation with the project coordination & management team, work package leaders team members are responsible for the integration of their results into succeeding project activities.

2.3.2 External Bodies

Advisory Board (AB): It will include a panel of four (4) independent experts not involved in the day-to day project work. This panel will closely monitor and directly provide consultation to the innovation and technological development activities performed by the consortium participants throughout the project's lifecycle. The ENTRUST consortium have already established strong relationships with pioneers in the key technology fields of the project, both in the research and industry communities focus on cybersecurity in healthcare. The AB will participate in project meetings or reviews, whereas UNIS will be responsible for its liaison along with MI, as dedicated resources in terms of budget have already been allocated to the latter.

3 Implementation Aspects

3.1 Decision Making

Decisions regarding the project implementation will normally be taken by the team members upon reaching consensus with the WP leaders. Typically, agreement will be reached first by informal contact, followed by official confirmation via electronic mail, letter or agreed written minutes. In case there is a dispute between two or more team members, a conflict resolution procedure should be followed, as presented in the specific document.

For important issues, the agreement may take the form of a short report that needs to be signed by the Steering Committee. Non-technical factors such as resource allocation and contractual terms will also need to be agreed and documented in writing.

The key driver on the decision-making procedures is the description of work to be performed as stated in the Contract, the CA, the Description of Action (DoA) and the Quality Plan, and as regularly communicated within the consortium. Transparency of the implementation decisions and actions will be achieved by adequate communication of the emerging issues on project meetings and e-mail communications.

3.2 Conflict Resolution

Generally, technical issues or conflicts within the contractual commitments that do not involve any contract, budget, resource allocation or overall project focus changes will be discussed at work package level first.

If the decision reached between team members is unacceptable by other partners, the conflict will be resolved according to a conflict resolution procedure which can be summarized in the next steps:

1. The team members involved in the implementation of the work package will inform the WP leader for the emerging conflict.
2. The WP leader will decide whether the issue needs to be discussed in a teleconference or a dedicated WP Meeting. The WP Leader will inform the Project Coordinator for the planned actions.
3. The result of the teleconference or the meeting will be communicated to the Project Coordinator.

4. If no consensus has been reached so far, the Project Coordinator will contact the responsible persons and will try to resolve the conflict.
5. In case that the disagreement remains, the issue will be escalated in the Steering Committee. The decision that will be taken at this level will be considered as the final resolution of the issue.

4 Reporting Procedure and Payment Arrangements

The project reporting is the procedure used by the European Commission (EC) to assess and follow up on the financed projects. Therefore, it is of utmost importance, as it conditions in a very direct way the good image and good assessment of the project by the EC. It is important to remark that the project reporting is a responsibility of the whole Consortium and every partner has to be actively involved in it. The Project Coordinator is the responsible for periodically gathering the information and reports from the different partners and consolidating it before sending it to the EC.

There are two types of reporting documents including technical and financial information: the Project Periodic Report and the Internal Activity Report. The Project Periodic Report refers to the official report that must be submitted to the EC according to the EC guidelines and templates. The Internal Activity Report refers to internal documents that will be used as control measures to effectively monitor the technical and economic progress of the ENTRUST project. The Internal Activity Reports will also feed the official reports.

4.1 Reporting Procedures

4.1.1 Internal Activity Report

ENTRUST Internal Activity Reports have to be prepared by consortium partners and provided to the Project Coordinator two times per year (every 6 months). An Internal Activity Report shall contain: (a) Technical Information about the WP progress as provided by the respective WP leaders, (b) Effort Information as all partners will be requested to provide a breakdown of the effort spent in the related semester, per WP in comparison to the planned effort.

The procedure to be followed is:

- At the end of the 6-month period, the Project Coordinator will send to the consortium an

email with instructions and template to be filled in;

- Each Partner has to fill in:
 - a) Short description of the work done (per WP and Task)
 - b) Achievements and results
 - c) Problems occurred
 - d) Brief overview of planned activities for upcoming semester
 - e) Overview of dissemination/exploitation/cooperation/standardisation activities
 - f) An estimation of resources spent (PMs) per WP in the respective reporting semester against the actual total PMs per WP
- The partners send their report to the Project Coordinator; this has to happen 20 days after the closure of the period
- Finally, the Project Coordinator consolidates the Internal Activity Report and shares it with the consortium once finalised.

4.1.2 Project Periodic Reports

During the ENTRUST project, two official Project Periodic Reports must be submitted to the EC by the Project Coordinator, covering the periods P1 (from Month 1 to Month 18), P2 (from Month 19 to Month 36). The reports shall be submitted to the EC for each reporting period within 60 days after the end of the period under assessment. The delay in the submission of these reports may cause the postponement of part of the next payment to be received by the partner until the next reporting period. The technical part will be managed through corresponding Project Periodic Reports. The Project Coordinator is in charge to prepare the specific reports based on the information provided through Internal Activity Reports.

The financial status of the project and costs incurred during the period must be communicated to the EC through meticulously prepared Financial Statements (FS) in order to justify the incurred costs and expenses and qualify for the next/final payment. Each consortium partner has to upload

financial information to the EC participant portal (EU Login System) based on cumulative information obtained from the Interim Activity Report.

The procedure to be followed is:

- The Project Coordinator will ask the partners to generate their individual Financial Statements in the EC Participant Portal to officially declare the costs incurred for the reference period;
- Each partner will complete the financial statements with the costs incurred during the period;
- Each partner will submit and digitally sign the FS. This signature will be done by the Project Financial Signatory appointed; and
- The Project Coordinator will submit the financial report to the EC;

4.1.3 Project Final Report

In addition to the final Periodic report, a Final Report has to be submitted by the coordinator 60 days after the end of the last reporting period.

4.2 Payment Schedule

The payment schedule, which contains the transfer of pre-financing and interim payments to Parties, will be handled according to the following:

Given that the amount of the pre-financing payment was 4,506,470.00 € (80% of the Maximum Grant Amount) and the amount of 281,654.38 € corresponding to 5% of the Maximum Grant Amount will be retained by the Funding Authority from the pre-financing payment and transferred into the 'Guarantee Fund', funding of costs included in the Consortium Plan will be paid to Parties after receipt from the Funding Authority without undue delay and in conformity with the provisions of the GA. Costs accepted by the Funding Authority will be paid to the Party concerned.

- For the payment of the balance (final payment); the provisions of the GA will be followed.
- Costs accepted by the Funding Authority, pertaining to interim and final payments, will be paid to Parties after receipt from the Funding Authority within 30 days and in conformity with the provisions of the GA.

- Payments shall be made following confirmation of each Party's bank account details.

The Project Coordinator is entitled to withhold any payments due to a Party identified by a responsible Consortium Body to be in breach of its obligations under this CA or the GA or to a Beneficiary which has not yet signed this CA.

The Project Coordinator is entitled to recover any payments already paid to a Defaulting Party. The Project Coordinator is equally entitled to withhold payments to a Party when this is suggested by or agreed with the Funding Authority.

4.3 Management of Knowledge and Intellectual Property

Knowledge and intellectual property issues will be addressed in compliance to HEU contract template/contractual conditions. Such issues include ownership and protection of knowledge, dissemination of knowledge, access rights, etc. as described in the Consortium Agreement that is dully signed by all partners.

The Steering Committee will be in charge of monitoring the proper implementation of the conditions specified in the Contract and the CA. Special emphasis within the project will be given to the management of knowledge (whether background or Results) and more importantly to the protection of IPRs, as well as to the management of ownership of the project results. Upon the project success, the Project Coordination & Management Team will develop a detailed Exploitation Agreement which will be signed by all partners, regulating obligations and rights of the participants.

To optimally manage the IPR and maintain an expanded Results Ownership List (ROL) as dictated by new HEU guidelines, the ENTRUST IPR team lead by SMNS will:

1. Adhere to the official [IPRHelpdesk.eu](https://www.iprhelpdesk.eu) guidelines as updated from H2020 to HEU
2. Adhere to the **STL IP Licensing** Manual of the World Intellectual Property Organisation (WIPO) and the International Trade Centre (ITC), as endorsed and recommended by HEU guidelines
3. Include a seasoned **IP Attorney** and an experienced **IP Marketing** specialist in the IPR team
4. Employ the IP concepts clarified within the **Common Exploitation Booster (CEB)**

5. Since the beneficiaries of the ENTRUST offerings will also include governmental entities, policy makers, supranational organisations and standardisation bodies, ENTRUST will also adopt the **Fair, Reasonable, and Non-Discriminatory** (FRAND) licensing commitment towards them, as required for licensed-copyrighted assets which protect and improve the lives of the general public (Obligatory, i.e., as in the case of vaccines).

Produced IPR output, will be recursively updated twice (2) per year, according to the renowned methodologies and best practices above:

1. **Exploitable Asset/Result Taxonomy** including not only direct project produced assets, but also cross-adopted assets within the ecosystem such as external datasets employed, respecting previous royalties where applicable.
2. **Inclusion of “Intangibles”** such as patents, journal publications, methodologies and frameworks, royalties of the marketplace/ecosystem and its community, pilot produced intangible knowledge, trainings, articles/posts etc.
3. **ROL** with clear depictions of Background, Foreground, Side-ground, and cross references per asset and per partner.
4. **Beyond the ROL the IPR Claims Master Registry** will be produced, with yearly revisions and approval by all partners, illustrating Assistive Contribution Levels, and the Contribution-Benefits Matrix (typical action-oriented IPR methodology) to mitigate risks of disputes (amicable conflict resolution).
5. **Maintain the Project Knowledge Registry** within the program office, and ensure background entries within the CA and also the proper Access Rights to Background and Results.
6. **Preferred licensing for developed toolboxes and software** in the marketplace is Open-Source code, as the central aim of the consortium is to provide benefit to the European community
7. **Joint Workshops** with the marketplaces/success-stories (as per dissemination Key Performance Indicators) shall always devote a session on the IPR updates and unanimous acceptance by the consortium members. Importantly, all Key Exploitable Results and if needed, ENTRUST datasets, services, tools, and data spaces will be submitted in the

officially recommended EC platforms (i.e., Digital Single Market “Innovation Radar”, etc.).

ENTRUST consortium will also make sure to take appropriate measures to avoid any situation that could lead to misuse of our results. In addition, it will guarantee a secure information exchange and transfer of knowledge through Non-Disclosure Agreements (NDAs) between EU and no-EU partners from the UK, Switzerland and Turkey. These measures are detailed in the CA.

5 Deliverable Submission and Quality Management

5.1 Deliverable Submission

The different technical objectives set for the project have their correspondence within the work packages and defined tasks. Compliance with these technical objectives is evident by on-time delivery the corresponding Deliverables. Each deliverable is assigned to Lead Beneficiary partners who will be responsible of its elaboration in due date. Every Lead Beneficiary is fully responsible for the deliverable's quality and is required to maintain adequate control of the participants' contributions.

The deliverables shall be submitted to the EC in English, by electronic means (in pdf format in the Participants Portal) or in any other format only if required by EC. The appropriate and updated deliverable template can be found in the ENTRUST Project Repository.

All the deliverables must be finalised and submitted to the EC within the deadlines defined in Annex I of the GA.

The process to be followed for the deliverable preparation and submission is (see Figure 2):

1. Lead beneficiary responsible for preparation of first draft
2. Lead beneficiary sends the completed deliverable draft to the Project Coordinator one month before the contractual submission date (M_{x-1})
3. The Project Coordinator checks the quality of the report and forwards it to the assigned internal reviewers
4. Comments from the Project Coordinator and the internal reviewer(s) to be sent to the editor within 7 days
5. Update done by the editor within 7 days
6. Approval by Project Coordinator and if necessary, by reviewer within 4 days
7. Final check/release and submission to the EC within 3 days and until the actual submission deadline

Figure 2 – Deliverable submission timeline

The assigned internal reviewers will have available an Internal Review Report template, provided by the Project Coordinator, to document in a structured way their comments and feedback. The review template examines specific criteria addressing readability, structure and conformance to template categories.

Moreover, during the Kick-off Meeting, the Consortium has decided and assigned 2 internal reviewers in most of the deliverables, as presented in Table 1, based on partners’ expertise.

Table 1 – Assigned internal reviewers

Del. No.	Deliverable Title	Lead beneficiary	Type	Diss. level	Due Date	Reviewer 1	Reviewer 2
D1.1	Project Handbook	UNIS	Report	PU	3	SL	PARTICLE
D1.2	Data Management Plan V1	FN	DMP	SEN	6	UNIS	S5
D1.3	Legal and Ethical issues and Guidelines	FN	Report	PU	24	MI	RA
D1.4	Data Management Plan V2	FN	DMP	SEN	18	SINTEF	UNIS
D2.1	ENTRUST Reference Architecture – Initial Release	UBITECH	Report	PU	12	UMU	RA
D2.2	ENTRUST Reference Architecture – Final Release	UMU	Report	PU	24	UBITECH	TUE
D3.1	Trust Abstractions & Cryptographic Anchors for CMD Secure Operation	SMNS	Report	PU	15	TUE	UPRC
D3.2	ENTRUST Risk Assessment & Collective Threat Intelligence Framework – Initial	TUE	Other	PU	18	SMNS	SURREY

	Release						
D3.3	ENTRUST Trust & Risk Assessment Framework – Final Release	SINTEF	Other	PU	30	UBITECH	SMNS
D4.1	Conceptual architecture of ENTRUST Customizable TC and Attestation Models Specifications	QUBITECH	Other	PU	15	SURREY	UMU
D4.2	Runtime Assurance & Certification Framework – First Release	SURREY	Other	PU	18	TUE	SINTEF
D4.3	Runtime Assurance & Certification Framework – Final Release	UMU	Other	PU	30	SINTEF	SURREY
D5.1	ENTRUST Blockchain Architecture, Authorization and Secure On- and Off-Chain Data Management – First Release	S5	Other	PU	18	UPRC	UBITECH
D5.2	ENTRUST Continuous Authorization, Trust Management, Monitoring Mechanisms and Trust Evidence Collection	UPRC	Other	PU	30	S5	SPH
D6.1	Integrated Framework (First Release) and Use Case Analysis	SPH	Other	SEN	21	KARD	POLARIS
D6.2	Integrated Framework (Final Release), Use Case Evaluation and Project Impact Assessment	SMNS	Other	SEN	36	SPH	SL
D7.1	Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation Plan	UPRC	Report	PU	6	FN	MI
D7.2	Impact Maximization Activities Interim Report	UMU	Report	PU	15	TLU	FN
D7.3	Impact Maximization Activities Final Report	RA	Report	SEN	36	FN	MI

D7.4	ENTRUST Website design and release	UPRC	DEC	PU	6	KARD	FN
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5.2 Document Control Management

The Document Control Management deals with the preparation of template documents, the identification and the tracking of changes related to draft and final versions of documents circulated among the partners.

The Project Coordinator is responsible for the necessary assessment of deliverables, while the Quality Manager will be responsible for the overall monitoring of the entire document control and configuration management activities described in this section.

5.3 Document Requirements

In the span of the ENTRUST project, a set of deliverables and relevant documented results are anticipated as depicted in the following table (Table 2). Such documents will be sent by e-mail and be uploaded in the restricted ENTRUST document repository, as long as they comply with the following standards:

- Word Processor: Microsoft Word 2007 and higher,
- Spreadsheet: Microsoft Excel 2007 and higher,
- Presentations: Microsoft PowerPoint 2007 and higher.

All files should be scanned for potential viruses before issue and screened on receipt. If an acknowledgement is requested, an explicit request should be included by the sender at the top of the message (e-mail, fax, etc.).

Table 2 – Type of files

Type	Responsible	Template
Deliverable submitted to the EC	As per DoA	Deliverable Document Template
Internal Project Presentation	All partners	Project Presentation Template
Meeting Agenda	Project Coordinator	Project Meeting Agenda
Meeting Minutes	Project Coordinator & Technical Coordinator	Meeting Minutes Template
Reviewed Document	All partners	A new version with track changes on the original version

Internal Review Report	All partners	Internal Review Report Template
Final Activity Report	Project Coordinator / WP Leaders	As per Grant Agreement and Commission guidelines
Final Management Report	Project Coordinator	As per Grant Agreement and Commission guidelines
Financial Statement	All Partners	As per Grant Agreement and Commission guidelines
Consolidated Statement	Financial Administrator	As per Grant Agreement and Commission guidelines

5.3.1 Naming Conventions and Versioning

Document configuration management will be ensured through tracking the versions and the history of changes within the various project documents, such as:

- Deliverables (as stated in the deliverables list in the DoA);
- Presentations of the project results;
- Meeting agenda and minutes; and
- Internal audit reports and reviewed deliverables, including the corrective actions taken.

Document history will be tracked in each deliverable in a separate table describing the different versions of the document and the reasons of change/updates on it.

Document versioning will be tracked through the monitoring of the Configuration Matrix in which all versions of each document will be tracked.

5.3.2 Deliverables submitted to the EC

Name	ENTRUST – [Deliverable Code]-[Deliverable Title]-vA.BB
Where	A: Major version of the deliverable (Submission to Commission) BB: Minor version of the deliverable for updates during the preparation phase
Examples	ENTRUST – D1.1-Project Handbook-v1.00 (for submission to the Commission) ENTRUST – D1.1-Project Handbook _UNIS-v0.30 (for internal updates and submission for internal review)

5.3.3 Internal Project Presentations

Name	ENTRUST – [Purpose] or [WP Number] [Partner]-vA.BB
Where	A: Major version of the presentation (Presentation in the event / workshop) BB: Minor version of the presentation for updates during the preparation phase
Examples	ENTRUST – WP1_UNIS-v1.00

5.3.4 Meeting Agenda

Name	ENTRUST – [Meeting Number] Meeting_Agenda_[Place]-vA.BB
Where	A: Major version of the meeting agenda BB: Minor version of the meeting agenda for updates during the preparation phase Place: Venue city
Examples	ENTRUST – KOM Agenda_Athens-v1.00 (final version) ENTRUST – KOM Agenda_Athens-v0.10 (for internal updates and submission for internal review)

5.3.5 Meeting Minutes

Name	ENTRUST – [Meeting Number] Meeting_Minutes_[Place]-vA.BB
Where	A: Major version of the meeting minutes BB: Minor version of the meeting minutes for updates during the preparation phase Place: Venue city
Examples	ENTRUST – KOM Minutes_Athens-v1.00 (final version) ENTRUST – KOM Minutes_Athens-v0.10 (for internal updates and submission for internal review)

5.3.6 Reviewed Documents and Internal Audit Reports

Name	ENTRUST – [Deliverable Code]-[TR/QR]_[Partner / Expert]-vA.BB
Where	A: Major version of the deliverable / internal audit report BB: Minor version of the deliverable / internal audit report for updates during the preparation phase TR: Technical Reviewed document QR: Quality Reviewed document
Examples	ENTRUST – D1.1-TR_U-v0.31 (Technical Reviewed Document from UNIS) ENTRUST – D1.1-TR_UNIS -v0.31 (Review report from UNIS) ENTRUST – D1.1-TR_UNIS -v0.41 (Quality Reviewed Document from UNIS)

5.3.7 Security Levels

Circulation of Deliverables, Internal Deliverables and Working Documents, inside and outside the ENTRUST Consortium, is subject to the rules associated to the following security levels (Table 3):

Table 3 – Deliverable Security Levels

Type	Responsible	Template
PU	Public	Free circulation inside and outside the Consortium

SE	Sensitive	Circulation is limited to members of the Consortium, the Commission Staff and the Reviewers
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As a general rule, the European Commission Services have free access to all the Deliverables and Internal Deliverables produced by the Project.

5.3.8 Code of Conduct

ENTRUST partners are expected to jointly develop new ideas, concepts, and architectures, as well as to pursue, jointly or individually, relevant opportunities for dissemination and exploitation of the project results. Therefore, in order to guarantee open and frank collaboration among the consortium members, namely when this involves original contributions and information subject to some level of confidentiality, the following principles shall be observed:

- The partners shall comply to the rules set by Annex II to the Contract (General Conditions) and by the ENTRUST CA, in relation to:
 - The Intellectual Property Rights, regarding any original contribution or background knowledge brought in by any member; and
 - The IPR regarding any new knowledge (forward knowledge) generated in the framework of ENTRUST as a result of any cooperative activity.
- In all forms of use of the mentioned knowledge, proper recognition to all original contributors should be made, namely through:
 - Proper references in publications. When the referenced piece of knowledge has been published, standard referencing rules should apply. In case of draft ideas included in working documents, a reference to the author and corresponding document should be made; and
 - Otherwise, in the case that there is no written reference, a note stating: "personal communication in the framework of the ENTRUST project" can be used (identifying the contributor).
- Similar rules should be observed when using copies of slides that include substantial original ideas (figures or text).
- When reporting Research and Technical Development (RTD) results, Deliverables and Working Documents will contain a list of the contributing partners, intended as physical persons of the involved organizations who have provided contributions to the document.

6 Communication amongst Consortium partners

Efficient communication and collaboration structures are essential for the success of the project. Since all project partners are distributed across European member states, the centrepiece of the overall project communication will be a protected online collaboration platform, offering to each partner independent access to important documents, code, meeting agendas, supporting materials, individual to-do lists and other miscellaneous project information.

6.1 Meetings and Workshops

Regular and ad-hoc meetings will be held during the project lifecycle, including:

- **Project Plenary Meetings** held every 4 months, approximately, in order to ensure that all procedures are understood and implemented in the proper way.

The Project Coordinator is responsible for the meeting formation (agenda of the meeting) and the communication of the meeting details (time, place) at least 2 weeks before the date of the meeting, in order to allow time to the participants for the scheduling and preparation of the necessary information for the meeting.

Technical Partners Meetings held per case if required. Those meetings will be organised by the Technical Coordinator.
- **Online Work Package Meetings** held approximately every 15 days according to the workload and performed through the teleconferencing facilities of the project.

Each WP leader will propose the meeting schedule according to his WP needs at least 1 week before the date of the meeting and coordinate the necessary actions among the involved partners for the implementation of the WP activities. Each WP leader will communicate the final agenda of the meeting at least 1 day before the meeting date.
- **Regular Conference Calls, Plenary Calls** will be held on a monthly basis. Proposed Date: first Thursday of the month Time: 11.00 CET. Regular or ad-hoc conference calls related to specific work packages will be requested by Work package Leaders. The Coordinator will host the Plenary Meetings employing Google Workspace platform.

A tentative table of the project meetings is available below (Table 4).

Table 4 – Tentative List of ENTRUST Plenary Meetings

Event	Date	Place
Kick-off meeting	18-19 January 2023	Athens, GR
1 st Plenary Meeting	April 2023	TBD

2nd Plenary Meeting	September 2023	TBD
3rd Plenary Meeting	December 2023	TBD
4th Plenary Meeting and RP1	March 2024	TBD
5th Plenary Meeting	June 2024	TBD
6th Plenary Meeting	September 2024	TBD
7th Plenary Meeting	December 2025	TBD
8th Plenary Meeting	March 2025	TBD
9th Plenary Meeting	September 2025	TBD
Final Meeting and RP2	January 2026	TBD

6.2 Mailing Lists

Effective channels of internal communication have been established from M1 in order to exchange all the necessary information for the project implementation, such as deliverables and relevant documentation. Internal communication channels are also used for exchanging meeting minutes and progress reports, ensuring a common understanding among all partners regarding the required achievements during the lifetime of the project as well as the procedures that have to be followed for fulfilling them.

A set of e-mail distribution lists have been created to facilitate the communication flows within the different bodies of the consortium. Subscription of each project member to a specific mailing list is managed and maintained by the Project Coordinator. The updated subscription list is available through the ENTRUST Project Repository. Each consortium partner is responsible to inform the Project Coordinator whether any modification of their representatives is needed, and the Project Coordinator will be responsible for keeping the distribution lists updated and informing the rest of members.

6.3 Project collaborative space – Infrastructure and Repository

UNIS along with UBITECH deployed and will continue to operate the internal Documents and Electronic Material Repository. A brief summary of the documentation organization and content of the ENTRUST Project Repository with respect to the Document Management System is presented below:

- 01_Administrative Documents: It contains the participants' contacts details as well as all the documents promoting the smooth progress of the project (risk monitoring, assigned reviewers list etc.)

- 02_Legal Documents: Contractual documents, containing the GA with EC and its annexes and the CA with its annexes.
- 03_Work Packages: A folder per Work package is created. In each WP folder, separate folders per Deliverable are also created. In each Deliverable folder, the consortium will store the material files required, the various contributions, the deliverable's editing versions, the review reports, as well as the final draft and the submitted deliverable to the EC.
- 04_Meetings: The specific folder contains the files that refer to Meetings Agendas, Meetings Minutes, as well as Meetings Partners Presentations. Furthermore, it contains the folder structure to support the storage of all Teleconferences Presentations and Minutes describing the decisions made and action plans produced.
- 05- Submitted Deliverables: The specific folder contains the list of the PDF files of the deliverables as these will be officially uploaded to EU Login System.
- 06_Reporting: It encloses a financial reporting folder created where all financial related documents will be stored for the ENTRUST reporting periods
- 07_Templates: It contains the created documents' templates to be utilized

Figure 3 – ENTRUST File repository - Homepage

7 Risk Management Plan

The risk management plan has been produced on the basis of existing risk management practices and more specifically the Continuous Risk Management (CRM) paradigm developed by the Software Engineering Institute (SEI) of Carnegie Mellon University [2]. It aims at reporting risk identification, analysis and mitigation strategies for the ENTRUST project.

7.1 Overview

Successful implementation of any kind of project relies, amongst others, on timely identification and control of risks, foreseeing of the consequences and effective management of them via appropriate proactive actions. Project risks describe the impact on the project of circumstances such as diminished quality of the end results, increased costs, delivery delays, loss of community confidence, or even failure. Risks' possibilities as well as risks' impact should neither be neglected nor overrated. Being efficient and effective in identifying and performing all proactive actions regarding possible risks will aid towards achieving the challenging ENTRUST objectives on time and according to budget; risk identification, management and mitigation constitutes, therefore, an integral part of the overall project management approach.

Risk management incorporates the following activities:

- Assessing continuously what could go wrong (risks);
- Determining which risks are important to deal with; and
- Implementing strategies to deal with those risks.

7.1.1 Continuous Risk Management Approach

According to [2], the CRM paradigm that will be followed during the entire lifecycle of ENTRUST project contains the following elements:

- **Identify:** makes all known project risks explicit before they become problems;
- **Analyse:** transforms risk data into decision-making information;
- **Plan:** translates risk information into decisions and mitigating actions (both present and future) and implements those actions;
- **Track:** monitors risk indicators and mitigation actions;
- **Control:** corrects deviations from the risk mitigation plans; and
- **Communicate:** enables the sharing of all information throughout the project and is the cornerstone of effective risk management.

Figure 4 – CRM paradigm followed in ENTRUST

7.1.2 Risk Exposure

Risk exposure is a measure created by combining the impact and probability of the risk. These terms are identified below at the level of detail compliant to that of the SEI (four levels of impact and three of probability, translating to different levels of risk exposure).

Effect / Impact: the effect of the particular risk on the project, which is determined on the basis of the risk’s effect on the project (e.g., performance, cost, schedule). The levels of impact are: (4) Uncontrollable, (3) Critical, (2) Marginal and (1) Negligible.

Probability: the chance that a particular impact will occur. The levels of probability are: (3) High, (2) Medium and (1) Low.

Risk exposure as a function of probability and impact is computed in.

Table 5 – Risk Exposure

Effect/Impact Probability	High	Medium	Low
Uncontrollable	High	High	Medium
Critical	High	Medium	Medium
Marginal	Medium	Medium	Low
Negligible	Medium	Low	Low

For risks where exposure is medium or high, specific mitigation strategies shall be put in place and acted upon.

7.1.2 Risk Monitoring

The project will continuously monitor and assess identified risks and pay specific attention to risks that have been ranked as with high and medium exposure. To that end, an online, live risk management document has been created and shared among ENTRUST partners through the official project’s repository.

Within the DoA, 14 risks have been identified and are monitored since the beginning of the project. In addition to the risks that have been determined during the proposal stage and reported via the EC Participant Portal, WP leaders should include new entries in the risk register file in case they identify new risks, during the early stages of the project. The risk register document can be found at the official project’s repository (<https://ubitecheu.sharepoint.com/sites/ENTRUST>), under Administrative Documents folder.

Number	WP	Risk description	Probability	Impact	Proposed Mitigation Measures	Who mitigates	Status	Priority	Check Resp.	Check Date	Reference Period	Mitigation Measures applied	Risk Mitigation	Comments, if the risk mitigation measure does not fit the table, please indicate
1	WP1	Coordination - Lack of experience due to the departure of key member	Medium	Medium	Partners will manage technical viability according to allocated alternative personnel in case of departure of this personnel	UNES	Open		UNES		1 or 2 or both	yes/no	yes/no	
2	WP1	Coordination - Delays caused by not meeting the tasks deadline	Medium	Medium	Partners involved in delayed tasks will allocate further resources to meet deadline. Regular project management and regular calls will mitigate the risk of falling behind activities	UNES, UB	Open		UNES		1 or 2 or both	yes/no	yes/no	
3	WP2, WP3	Technical - Requirements do not satisfy use case implementation	Low	High	Collaboration between academic, industry & pilot partners will require discussion and feedback requirements. Reference architecture can be adapted to respond to new needs for WP users	UNES, UB, SPH	Open		UNES		1 or 2 or both	yes/no	yes/no	
4	WP3, WP4	Technical - Risk Assessment methodology not complete	Medium	Medium	Joint research activities with WP3 & WP4 for better representation of the needs of the ENTRUST integral components	UB, SPH, UNES	Open		UNES		1 or 2 or both	yes/no	yes/no	
5	WP4	Technical - CMs contractual measures insufficient to run ENTRUST TC	Medium	Medium	The design of TC will consider a mixture of tasks of the use of technical resources experience (the DICE) together with the design of economic high level (H) for the procurement of these use alternative components that need to run in real-time	UB, UB	Open		UNES		1 or 2 or both	yes/no	yes/no	
6	WP5	Technical - Lack of specific data and data sources for the training of the AI models	Low	High	Use case partners are highly engaged in the respective application domains, experienced in generating enriched data enabling the robust use, making this not very unlikely to happen	UB, UPIC	Open		UNES		1 or 2 or both	yes/no	yes/no	
7	WP4, WP5	Technical - Lack of interfaces for secure and efficient data management from SW based elements	Low	High	There are existing Blockchain technologies and the consortium (UPIC, UB) has well established in the previous grant phases interfaces and on the responsibility between Blockchain and based computing elements	UPIC, UB, UB	Open		UNES		1 or 2 or both	yes/no	yes/no	

Figure 5 – ENTRUST online document for real time risk monitoring

References

- [1] ISO, GOST R. "Quality management systems–Requirements." ISO, Geneva, 2015.
- [2] [Online], Available: <http://www.sei.cmu.edu>. [Accessed 2 December 2022]

